

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins. Part II*

V. N. Dholakia and K. N. Trivedi

4-Hydroxycoumarin has been condensed with malic acid to yield benzopyranyl (3,2-c) pyran-2,8-dione which has been brominated to 9-bromo derivative and the latter degraded to 4*H*-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-4-one. 4-Hydroxycoumarin, 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin and 4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin have been similarly condensed with ethyl acetoacetate and degraded to corresponding 3-methyl-4*H*-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-4-ones.

Arora and Mathur¹ reported that coumarino(3',4',5,6)-4-methyl-3-phenyl- α -pyrone possesses anticoagulant activity comparable to dicoumarol. 4*H*-furo-(3,2-c)benzopyran-4-one is likely to possess anticoagulant activity, as it is a dehydrated product of the hypothetical compound (IV), as suggested by Chmielewska and Cieslak². It was thought of interest to synthesise different benzopyranyl (3,2-c) pyran-2,8-diones and degrade them to 4*H*-furo-(3,2-c) benzopyran-4-ones according to the method developed by Trivedi and Sethna³ which consists of bromination of coumarino- α -pyrones, followed by ring contraction with alkali.

4-Hydroxycoumarin on the Pechmann condensation with malic acid in presence of 80% sulphuric acid gave benzopyranyl (3,2-c) pyran-2,8-dione (Ia) which, on bromination, gave 9-bromo derivative (Ie). This 9-bromo derivative on hydrolysis with 10% sodium carbonate solution afforded 4*H*-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-4-one-2-carboxylic acid (IIa) which on decarboxylation gave 4*H*-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-4-one (IIIb).

4-Hydroxycoumarin, 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin and 4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin were condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of 80% sulphuric acid or aluminium chloride to give 10-methylbenzopyranyl (3,2-c)-pyran-2,8-dione^{4,5} (Ib), 4,10-dimethylbenzopyranyl (3,2-c)-pyran-2,8-dione⁵ (Ic) and 6-methoxy-10-methylbenzopyranyl (3,2-c) pyran-2,8-dione (Id) respectively. These coumarino-4,3- α -pyrones on bromination gave corresponding 9-bromo derivatives (If, Ig, Ih) respectively. These 9-bromo derivatives when hydrolysed by refluxing 10% sodium carbonate solution gave 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) furan-3-carboxylic acids (IIa, IIb, IIc) respectively and not the corresponding 4*H*-furan(3,2-c) benzopyran-4-one-2-carboxylic acids. On hydrolysis of the bromo-derivatives (If, Ig, Ih), the compounds must have been degraded to coumarilic acids first, followed by decarboxylation to furocoumarins, the pyrone ring of which must have been opened up to give the above acids. These hydroxyacids were subsequently cyclised by

*Part I, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 563.

1. Arora and Mathur, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.* 1963, 20, 29.

2. Chmielewska and Cieslak, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 4, 135.

3. Trivedi and Sethna, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 563.

4. Mustafa, Hahmat, Zayed and Ahmed Nawar, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 1832.

5. Usgaonker and Patell, *this Journal*, 1965, 217.

refluxing hydrochloric acid to give 3-methyl-4*H*-furo (3,2-*c*) benzopyran-4-one (IIIc), 3,8-dimethyl-4*H*-furo (3,2-*c*) benzopyran-4-one (III*d*) and 3-methyl-7-methoxy-4*H*-furo (3,2-*c*) benzopyran-4-one (IIIe) respectively.

- Ia: $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$.
 b: $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$; $R_4=CH_3$.
 c: $R_1=R_4=H$; $R_2=R_3=CH_3$.
 d: $R_1=OCH_3$; $R_2=R_4=H$; $R_3=CH_3$.
 e: $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$; $R_4=Br$.
 f: $R_1=R_2=H$; $R_3=CH_3$; $R_4=Br$.
 g: $R_1=H$; $R_2=R_3=CH_3$; $R_4=Br$.
 h: $R_1=OCH_3$; $R_2=H$; $R_3=CH_3$; $R_4=Br$.

- IIa: $R_1=R_2=H$; $R_3=CH_3$.
 b: $R_1=H$; $R_2=R_3=CH_3$.
 c: $R_1=OCH_3$; $R_2=H$; $R_3=CH_3$.

- IIIa, $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$; $R_4=COOH$.
 b, $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$.
 c, $R_1=R_2=R_4=H$; $R_3=CH_3$.
 d, $R_1=R_4=H$; $R_2=R_3=CH_3$.
 e, $R_1=OCH_3$; $R_2=R_4=H$; $R_3=CH_3$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzopyranyl(3-2-*c*)pyran-2,8 dione (Ia).—A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (5.0 g.) and malic acid (5.0 g.) was heated on a steam bath with gradual addition of 80% H_2SO_4 (50 ml) in 45 min. period. Heating was continued for further 4 hr. The reaction mixture was added to ice and the product filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 242° ; yield 2.0 g. (Found: C, 67.21; H, 2.65. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.3; H, 2.81%).

9-Bromobenzopyranyl (3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (Ie).—Benzopyranyl (3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (2.0 g.) was dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid and bromine, dissolved in acetic acid (30 ml. 20%, 4 mole), was added and the mixture heated on a water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then added to ice and the bromo derivative filtered, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 211°, yield, 1.0 g. (Found: Br, 27.22. $C_{12}H_5O_4Br$ requires Br, 27.3%).

4H-Furo (3,2-c)benzopyran-4-one-2-carboxylic Acid (IIIa).—9-Bromobenzopyranyl (3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (1.0 g.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate solution (10 ml, 10%) for 45 min. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and acidified. The product was purified by dissolving it in sodium bicarbonate solution, reprecipitated and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 290°, yield, 0.4 g. (Found: C, 62.44; H, 3.07. $C_{12}H_6O_3$ requires C, 62.62; H, 2.6%).

4H-Furo (3,2-c)benzopyran-4-one (IIIb).—4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-4-one-2-carboxylic acid (0.4 g.) was heated on a sand bath with quinoline (5 ml) and copper bronze (0.2 g.) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid and filtered again. The filtrate was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The product obtained after evaporation of the ether was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 93°, yield, 0.1 g. (Found: C, 70.71; H, 3.1. $C_{11}H_6O_3$ requires C, 70.98; H, 3.22%).

9-Bromo-10-methylbenzopyranyl(3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (If)—10-Methylbenzopyranyl (3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (5.0 g.) was dissolved in hot acetic acid and a solution of bromine in acetic acid (35 ml) 20%, 2 mole) was added with stirring and the mixture left overnight. The separated bromo derivative was filtered, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 258°; yield, 2.5 g. (Found: Br, 26.15. $C_{13}H_7O_4Br$ requires Br, 26.06%).

2-(o-Hydroxyphenyl)-4-methylfuro-3-carboxylic Acid(IIa).—9-Bromo-10-methylbenzopyranyl (3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (2.0 g.) was refluxed with 10% sodium carbonate solution (20 ml) for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and acidified. The separated product was purified by treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution, and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 155°, yield, 0.8 g. (Found: C, 66.27; H, 4.38. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.06; H, 4.58%).

3-Methyl-4H-furo (3,2-c)benzopyran-4-one(IIIc).—2-(o-Hydroxyphenyl)-4-methylfuro-3-carboxylic acid (0.8 g.) was dissolved in ethanol and refluxed with hydrochloric acid for 4 hr. The separated product was filtered (charcoal) and crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 166°. yield, 0.2 g. (Found: C, 71.89; H, 4.001. $C_{11}H_8O_3$ requires C, 72.0; H, 4.6%).

9-Bromo-4,10-dimethylbenzopyranyl(3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (Ig).—4,10-Dimethylbenzopyranyl (3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (5.0 g.) was dissolved in hot acetic acid and bromine in acetic acid (33 ml, 20%, 2 mole) was added with stirring and the mixture kept overnight. The separated bromo derivative was filtered, dried and crystallised from acetic acid; m.p. 250°, yield 2.0 g. (Found: Br, 24.77. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4Br$ requires Br, 24.92%).

2-(2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-methylfuro-3-carboxylic Acid (IIb).—9-Bromo-4,10-dimethylbenzopyranyl (3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (2.0 g.) was refluxed with 10% sodium

carbonate solution (20 ml) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and acidified. The separated product was purified by treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 178°, yield, 0.7 g. (Found: C, 67.39; H, 4.75. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.17%).

3,8-Dimethyl-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-4-one(III d).—2-(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-4-methylfuro-3-carboxylic acid (0.7 g.) was dissolved in and refluxed with hydrochloric acid for 3 hr. The separated product was filtered (charcoal), washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from dil acetic acid, m.p. 157°, yield, 0.3 g. (Found: C, 72.59; H, 4.43. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.67%)

5-Methoxy-10-methylbenzopyranyl(3,2-c) pyran-2,8-dione (Id).—4-Hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (5.0 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (6.5 g.) were heated on steam bath with gradual addition of 80% sulphuric acid (50 ml.) for 45 min. Heating was continued for further 4 hr. The reaction mixture was added to ice and the product was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 237°, yield, 2.0 g.

A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (5.0 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (10.0 g.) was added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.5 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (30 ml). The reaction mixture was heated at 130° for 4 hr., then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid; nitrobenzene was steam-distilled. The product was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid; yield was 4.5 g. (Found: C, 65.16; H, 3.85. $C_{14}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 65.12; H, 3.87%).

9-Bromo-5-methoxy-10-methylbenzopyranyl(3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (Ih).—5-Methoxy-10-methylbenzopyranyl(3,2-c) pyran-2,8-dione (4.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid and bromine in acetic acid (14 ml, 20%, 1 mole) was added with stirring. The bromo derivative separating immediately was filtered, dried, and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 278°; yield, 3 g. (Found: Br, 23.6. $C_{14}H_9O_5$ Br requires Br, 23.74%).

2-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylfuro-3-carboxylic Acid (IIc).—9-Bromo-5-methoxy-10-methylbenzopyranyl(3,2-c)pyran-2,8-dione (2.0 g.) was refluxed with 10% sodium carbonate solution (20 ml) for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified. The product was filtered and purified by treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 201°; yield 0.8 g. (Found: C 62.77; H, 4.76. $C_{13}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 63.77; H, 4.45%).

3-Methyl-7-methoxy-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-4-one (IIIc).—2-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylfuro-3-carboxylic acid (0.8 g.) was dissolved in ethanol and refluxed with hydrochloric acid for 3 hr. The separated product was filtered (charcoal), washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid. m.p. 173°, yield, 0.2 g. (Found: C, 67.64; H, 4.22. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.82; H, 4.34%).

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